

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

SMART AGRICULTURE: THE FUTURE OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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Abstract

Smart agriculture is a revolution that aims to increase productivity and sustainability in the agricultural sector by integrating information and communication technologies. This article discusses how smart agriculture is transforming the agricultural sector and the benefits offered by modern technology.

Benefits of Modern Technology in Agriculture:

Increased Productivity: Effective use of inputs (water, fertilizer, medicine) provides a significant increase in product yield.

Cost Reduction: Reduces costs by eliminating unnecessary expenses.

Sustainability: Environmentally friendly practices are encouraged, resource consumption is reduced.

Product Quality: Product quality is monitored and controlled, higher quality products are obtained.

Technological Innovation: The agricultural sector becomes more modern, automated and efficient.

Food Safety and Traceability: Supply chain traceability increases, food safety is ensured.

Smart agriculture is a promising approach for the future of the agricultural sector. With the integration of modern technology, more efficient, sustainable and high-quality food production becomes possible. This change provides significant benefits for both farmers and consumers.

Keywords: agriculture, smart, technology, sustainable, production

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, problems such as climate change, increasing population, shrinking agricultural areas and decreases in the amount of usable water, aging agricultural population and migration indicate that there will be some bottlenecks in food and agricultural production in the future. In addition, the increase in land degradation and natural disasters, cross-border diseases, malnutrition and developments in agricultural trade policies are also likely to put pressure on the agricultural sector.

These expectations on the supply and demand sides indicate that the sustainability problem of agricultural production will arise in the future. This situation puts issues such as how to increase the production needed in agricultural production, how to minimize existing losses and how to achieve more efficiency per unit area among the most important priorities of countries. At this point, countries have started to allocate significant resources to a technological transformation in agriculture in R&D and innovation moves. Agricultural production, which was initiated by human beings to meet their individual needs, has turned into economic activity over time and has changed to meet the needs of the increasing population. With the globalization process and increasing competition, agricultural enterprises have begun to pay more attention to technological innovations to increase income and reduce costs in production. As the business structure shows a trend from small businesses to larger global producers, many technologies that were not widely used in agriculture before have become available in our country. With the

use of high technologies in agriculture, it helps farmers produce more agricultural products at less cost and contributes to safe, high-quality and sustainable food production. In this context, smart agricultural applications and many other information and communication technologies (mobile phones, internet, satellite images, remote sensing, sound waves, robots, advanced machines, etc.) have begun to be used at all stages from soil to fork within the agricultural value chain. In this way, the need for labor force began to decrease and the data could be collected and processed more frequently and accurately. In our country, there are many structural problems arising from marketing channels as well as agricultural production. If the technological transformation in question is supported by correct and permanent policies, it will provide significant benefits for this problem. In this context, it will be possible to ensure both profitability and traceability with digital developments in the logistics process on the one hand, and the widespread use of agricultural e-commerce applications on the other. The use of technology in the agricultural sector is changing, as in other sectors, and continues with a knowledge-intensive transformation. It is obvious that with this transformation, traditional production systems will evolve into more productive and innovative systems that use modern technology.

Information technologies are involved in every aspect of daily life to facilitate human life, undertake part or all of human work, and increase comfort. This change has led to the development of discoveries and inventions in the technologies used in agricultural pro-

duction. With the rapid developments in the last decades, the impact of information technologies on our living space is deepening and expanding. Information technologies have taken part in agriculture in recent years, as in other areas of life. Products and services based on research and development studies that have been going on for more than ten years are offered to the agricultural sector. In addition, with the diversification of financial resources in agricultural production, which is subject to global trade, it has become easier for global companies to access these resources and their costs have decreased significantly. This situation has had a negative impact on the competitiveness of small businesses. On the other hand, agricultural production serves as a sub-sector for other sectors in addition to food needs. In addition, it is in a position to provide added value to many sectors that make up the national economy, including itself. Considering that the basic raw materials of industrial production are based on agriculture, it may be a wrong perspective to reduce agricultural production only to the food sector. On the other hand, the agricultural sector is a social and economic area that affects the majority of our country's population. As a matter of fact, any negativity experienced in the sector affects all relevant stakeholders, especially consumers. In this respect, it is extremely important to implement and monitor an effective agricultural policy for the sector. One of the most important of these policies is policies based on technological transformation in agriculture. Many countries, especially the European Union, reflect the necessary moves in the technological field in their policies, based on the requirements of the digital age.

THE IMPORTANCE OF TECHNOLOGY IN AGRICULTURE

Information and communication technologies: covers a wide range of activities including the production/acquisition, processing/evaluation, storage, transfer and use of data. Many tools and equipment such as sensors, microprocessors, computers, satellites and software for data processing and conversion into usable form are currently being developed and offered to the end user. Raw data is compiled for a specific purpose, processed by mathematical and statistical means and converted into information. Human beings produce information only in their minds with the help of the information they produce. On the other hand, internet technology and communication technologies that enable the use of this technology also play an important role in sharing information, which is the processed form of data, and information produced/being produced in the human mind. Technical agricultural knowledge of producers/managers involved in agricultural production (principles of plant and animal breeding, combating diseases and pests, agricultural mechanization, etc.), agricultural policies and implementation decisions, production input markets and input prices, product markets and product prices, legislation and regulations. They need to have and use knowledge in a wide range of areas, including legal regulations and other issues. In addition to accessing this information, healthy, reliable and up-to-date data is needed for its use.

Significant technological developments have been experienced in the last decades by fusing agriculture and information technologies and managing this complex structure. For this reason, many new technical terms have begun to be heard in daily life. Examples of these terms include smart agriculture, precision agriculture, digital agriculture, e-farming, farm management software and driverless (autonomous) vehicles. Nowadays, the environmental impacts of agricultural production inputs and the pressure to reduce input costs are increasing with developing technology. This pressure is increasing in intensity due to the physical and geographical variability of agricultural lands, non-uniform soil, product and environmental factors, the impact of inputs on the environment and the increase in their costs. Smart agriculture envisages increasing "net income" (income - expense) by increasing efficiency in agricultural production through the effective use of inputs (in the required amount) and thus reducing its impact on the environment. This can also contribute to high product quality and uniformity in product quality. Agricultural technology covers all kinds of modern tools and all related services used as a requirement of new and advanced production technologies to increase product and work efficiency in agricultural enterprises where crop and animal production is carried out. Smart agriculture is an approach that aims to increase productivity through the integration of technology in the agricultural sector. It goes beyond traditional farming methods and offers various advantages to farmers. These advantages include achieving higher yields, reducing fertilizer and pesticide costs, improving product quality and environmentally friendly agricultural practices. Thanks to smart agriculture, monitoring and management of agricultural activities becomes easier, and realistic cost calculations can be made with instant data. Additionally, protection and monitoring processes can be managed more effectively during harvest periods. This approach encourages innovative practices in agricultural production by solving problems that are difficult to intervene in classical agriculture. For example, it ensures the dissemination of modern techniques such as soilless agriculture, thus increasing the sustainability and efficiency of agriculture.

Smart agriculture also offers a vision for the future of the agricultural sector that includes strategic planning and technological innovations. In this way, agricultural production processes become more predictable, offering farmers the potential for long-term economic gains. As a result, smart agriculture represents a new era in which modern agriculture evolves, benefiting both farmers and consumers.

Agricultural technologies facilitate business management while reducing the cost of work by increasing the efficiency of the human workforce.

SMART TECHNOLOGIES

AGRICULTURAL

Smart agriculture is an approach that makes agricultural production more efficient and sustainable through the use of technological tools and methods. Its main components are:

- **Sensors and IoT Devices:** It monitors soil, plant and climate conditions and collects data.
- **Smart Irrigation Systems:** Optimizes irrigation timing and amount.
- **Satellite and Drone Technologies:** It carries out field monitoring, mapping, planting, spraying and fertilization operations.
- **Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence:** It analyzes data to make predictions about disease risks, weather forecasts and crop productivity.
- **GPS and Geographic Information Systems (GIS):** It is used for precision agriculture applications.
- **Robotics and Automation:** It performs automatic planting, harvesting, spraying and fertilization.
- **Software and Mobile Applications:** Provides farm management and field data collection functions.

- **Blockchain Technology:** Increases supply chain traceability and food safety.
- **Energy Management Systems:** It ensures the use of renewable energy and energy efficiency.
- **Smart Storage and Logistics:** Monitors and manages product storage conditions.
- **Precision Agriculture:** Performs correct planting, fertilization and pesticide applications.
- **Climate and Weather Models:** Provides forecasts for planting and harvest timing.

These components aim to transform the agricultural sector by increasing the efficiency of agricultural activities, reducing costs and reducing environmental impacts.

According to the "Smart Agriculture Market Research" conducted by Huawei company in 2017, the value of the world smart agriculture market, which was 13.7 billion dollars in 2015, is expected to increase to 26.8 billion dollars in 2020. This means that the market will double in value with in 5 years.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) draw attention to the current situation in their studies and publications and make predictions about the problems that await us in the future. Indicators point to the fact that we do not have the agricultural production infrastructure to feed a population that could reach 10 billion worldwide by 2050. According to the United Nations 2019 World Food Security and Nutrition Report, 821.6 Million people are currently under the threat of hunger, while 670 Million adults and 120 Million children are fighting obesity. In addition to this unbalanced distribution, it is known that approximately one-third of the food is lost for various reasons in the process from the beginning of production to consumption.

In the CEMA (European Agricultural Machinery Association) Agriculture 4.0: Future of Agriculture Report, it is stated that there are 4,500 manufacturers in Europe producing 450 different agricultural machines,

with an annual turnover of 26 billion euros, and 135,000 people are employed in this sector. According to the same Report, 70% to 80% of new agricultural equipment sold in Europe includes a precision agriculture technology component. Another point emphasized in this Report is that smart agricultural practices will be the factor that will affect the agricultural sector the most by 2030 and will play a driving role in ensuring the sustainability of EU agriculture. The National Agriculture and Food Institute, which is affiliated with the Federal Department of Agriculture of the USA, one of the leading countries in the use of technology in agriculture, supports research in physics, engineering and computer science, the production of agricultural tools, sensors and software, and training farmers on how to use technology. On the other hand, the US Federal Department of Agriculture both provides incentives for integrated technologies for production and offers various support opportunities to farmers so that they can use agricultural technologies. With these incentives and supports, approximately 300 billion dollars worth of agricultural food products are produced annually in America. Israel supports agricultural technologies, especially irrigation systems, biotechnology and wastewater reuse. So much so that research and development expenditures in the

field of agricultural technologies constitute 17% of Israel's budget. New technological startup companies in the field of agricultural technology have a great impact on the transformation of the Israeli agricultural sector. According to the Annual Report on Food, Agriculture and Rural Areas (2016) published by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries of Japan, agricultural technologies are seen as the most important factor in reducing input costs. Thanks to technological developments, Japan's agricultural exports increased by 24%, generating an income of 35 billion dollars. The Japanese government continues its efforts to increase both the employment of the sector and the competitiveness of the country thanks to agricultural technologies. Current Situation in the EU: 86% of agricultural enterprises in the EU have an area below 20 ha. The European rural economy depends largely on small agricultural holdings. However, currently less than 25% of farmers have access to smart agriculture technologies. A Position Paper has been prepared by CEMA-European Agricultural Machinery Association on this subject, and in the document named "Smart Agriculture for All Enterprises"*, it is stated that smart agricultural technologies are suitable for farms under 100 ha (97% of agricultural enterprises in the EU). It was emphasized that if there is no action plan to support the procurement, it will be difficult for these farms to compete with farms in the USA, Canada and New Zealand. The document states that this situation will also be a problem for large agricultural enterprises that invest in such technologies. The Opinion Paper also includes the measures to be taken in the Common Agricultural Policies that will come into force after 2020, to ensure that smart agricultural technologies can reach a European farmer (enterprises between 50-100 ha), the role of smart technologies in increasing sustainability and environmental protection in agriculture, and which smart agricultural technologies should be encouraged. There are suggestions on what to do (Anonymous2019a).

One of the most important goals of Smart Agriculture is to automate the management of agricultural areas using modern information and communication technologies. Today, data collection in existing smart agriculture systems is achieved through the use of different types of sensors placed on different data collection platforms such as satellites, drones and agricultural robots. In addition to sensors that analyze water, light, humidity, temperature and chemicals to monitor morphological, physiological and biochemical changes in plants, the use of imaging sensors has become rapidly widespread in the last few years. With different imaging sensors, it is aimed for experts to examine plants autonomously and in real time, both visually and with other analysis methods. By using different imaging technologies, biochemical and physiological changes can be detected by imaging with visible and invisible wavelengths of plant parts such as leaf color, leaf texture, light reflectance rate. Sensors used in plant imaging can be examined in five different categories: RGB, spectroscopy, fluorescence, thermal and three-dimensional (3D) imaging. The common working principle of all imaging systems is that they measure the absorption of light sent to the imaged object. It has also been

shown that many different agricultural problems such as nutrient deficiency, plant diseases, pesticide use, pest detection can be solved with different imaging sensors in smart agricultural applications. It is seen that especially RGB and spectral imaging systems are more preferred in the smart agricultural systems being developed.

Images are collected using RGB and spectral cameras via satellites, drones and agricultural robots, which are frequently used in agriculture. With RGB imaging, color camera images are collected from many different electronic devices that are sensitive to red, green and blue (RGB) light bands, from mobile phones to computers that we frequently use in daily life. Spectral imaging is divided into two: "Multispectral" and "Hyperspectral". While Multispectral imaging captures images at specific wavelengths, Hyperspectral imaging records tens of wavelengths across a wide spectral bandpass. Images collected at different wavelengths with spectral cameras can characterize the color characteristics of cultivated agricultural fields and plants. Spectral imaging is an imaging tool frequently applied for nutrient, disease, insect, growth, pesticide and species detection analyzes in plants. Fluorescence imaging, thermal imaging and 3D imaging sensors are other imaging sensors used in smart agriculture technologies. These sensors are mostly used in laboratories and controlled crop growing areas. Due to its usage method, it is mostly preferred in manual or semi-autonomous smart agriculture systems. Fluorescence imaging is a technique in which UV-excited autofluorescence is collected from plants and is used in the analysis of plant metabolic activity. Thermal imaging creates an image of plant temperature and is used specifically to characterize sensitivity to drought. Thermal imaging is also used to investigate viral, bacterial and fungal infections. With 3D imaging sensors used in smart agriculture, 3D models of plants are created and width, height and depth information is extracted on this model. Monitoring and phenotyping plant growth is also possible with 3D imaging.

Another factor that makes smart and sensitive agricultural technologies necessary is the pollution of the environment and natural resources caused by agricultural production activities. Recently, chemical fertilizers and pesticides used unconsciously and in high amounts in plant and animal production cause pollution of the environment and natural resources (soil, air, water resources). The use of chemical fertilizers without soil and plant analysis and the unnecessary use of chemical pesticides for precautionary purposes are quite common. These chemical substances have the potential to pollute rainwater or irrigation water, underground and surface water resources, and harm other living creatures in the environment. Some research results on this subject are summarized below:

- In the US, more than 75% of states report agriculture as a significant threat to groundwater resources. At least one pesticide was found in more than 95% of samples taken from rivers and approximately 50% of samples taken from water wells. In Lake Erie in the USA, due to phosphorus sourced from agriculture, al-

gae density has formed in an amount that can be detected from satellite images, and this has reached a level that will harm human health, the creatures living in the lake and the environment.

- Excessive use of fertilizers can cause harmful effects on surface and groundwater (excessive amount of algae, undesirable odor and taste in drinking water, fish poisoning and fish death cases) (CAST, 2019).

- In Europe, 60% of the nitrogen and 25% of the phosphorus coming from rivers come from agriculture.

In the article titled "Reconsidering the crisis: Thirty years of failed agricultural policy" published on the website of the US-based think tank "Institute for Agriculture and Trade Policy (IATP)", which operates on agriculture-related issues (IATPa, 2020), agricultural The following information is briefly provided regarding the "pollution in natural resources" caused by production activities:

- Dramatic increases in the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides since the 1980s due to the increase in farm sizes in the USA and the intensification of livestock production further worsen water pollution.

- The majority of water resources are not suitable for the use of aquatic creatures and humans, and drinking water wells, especially in rural areas, are contaminated.

- In 2016, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) reported that 71% of lakes and ponds, 53% of rivers and streams, and 80% of bays and estuaries surveyed nationally did not meet water quality standards.

- The "Federal Clean Water Act (CWA)", enacted in 1972, aimed to "restore and protect the chemical, physical and biological integrity of waters" with "fishable" and "swimmable water" quality targets throughout the United States. However, these targets have not been achieved over time, and institutional failure to control agricultural pollutants has been an important reason for this.

- Laws aimed at controlling pollution from agriculture are weak in their implementation, the interests of large farms and agricultural enterprises, and protective standards and practices hinder the achievement of goals.

One of the factors that makes smart agriculture necessary is the need for healthy agricultural products. Chemical fertilizers and pesticides used excessively and unnecessarily can leave residues on agricultural products and cause various diseases (cancer, birth defects, reproductive system disorders, etc.) in humans and animals. With the use of smart and sensitive agricultural technologies, healthier agricultural products can be obtained by reducing the amount of chemical fertilizers and pesticides applied in agriculture.

CONCLUSION

Smart agriculture is an approach that aims to increase productivity by integrating information and communication technologies in the agricultural sector. It offers higher efficiency, lower costs and more sustainable applications by overcoming the limits of traditional methods. In light of the information discussed in this article, it can be said that smart agriculture provides

the following important contributions to the agricultural sector:

1. **Increased Productivity:** Smart agricultural technologies optimize processes such as irrigation, fertilization and spraying by monitoring soil, plant and climate conditions. In this way, effective use of inputs is ensured and significant increases in product yield are observed.

2. **Cost Reduction:** Sensors and data analysis eliminate unnecessary costs by enabling more efficient management of agricultural activities. Optimization of processes such as irrigation, fertilization and spraying contributes to more efficient use of resources and reduced costs.

3. **Sustainability:** Smart agriculture supports a sustainable agricultural model by encouraging environmentally friendly practices. Sensors monitor soil health and enable the determination of optimum fertilization and irrigation practices. This enables sustainable agricultural practices by preserving soil fertility and reducing environmental pollution.

4. **Product Quality:** Smart agricultural technologies support higher quality product production by providing the ability to monitor and control product quality. Data analysis determines the factors affecting product quality and ensures that necessary precautions are taken.

5. **Technological Innovation:** Smart agriculture brings technological innovation to the agricultural sector. The use of robotics, artificial intelligence, drones and other advanced technologies makes agricultural production more modern, automated and efficient. This increases the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and enables the development of more innovative products and services.

As a result, smart agriculture is a promising approach for the future of the agricultural sector, offering many benefits for farmers, consumers and the environment. By increasing efficiency, reducing costs and ensuring sustainability, smart agriculture contributes to the creation of a more efficient and sustainable food production system.

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References

1. Agriculture Innovation: 10 Tech Trends to Watch in 2023, <https://masschallenge.org/articles/agriculture-innovation/>
2. Anonymous 2019a. Website: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/publications/worldpopulation-prospects-2019-highlights.html>, Access Date: 11.08.2024.
3. Barnes, A.P., Soto, I., Eopry, V., Barbero, M.G., (2019), "Exploring the adoption of precision agricultural technologies: A cross regional study of EU farmers", *Land Use Policy* 80:163-174.
4. Ciruela-Lorenzo, A.M.; Del-Aguila-Obra, A.R.; Padilla-Meléndez, A.; Plaza-Angulo, J.J. Digitalization of agri-cooperatives in the smart agriculture context. Proposal of a digital diagnosis tool. *Sustainability* 2020. 12, 1325.

5. FAO's work on agricultural innovation, <https://www.fao.org/3/CA2460EN/ca2460en.pdf>
6. Elena Sira, Ryszard Pukala, MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURE INNOVATIONS: ROLE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT, Marketing and Management of Innovations, Issue 2, 2020, file:///C:/Users/K-Mobile%20service/Downloads/Management_of_agriculture_innovations_Role_in_Econ.pdf
7. Gurnule, P.V. Economical smart agriculture monitoring system. Int. J. Recent Technol. Eng. 2019, 8, 3669– 3671.
8. Griffin, T., Bongiovanni, R., Loweberg-DeBoer, J., (2010), "Worldwide Adoption of Precision Agriculture Technology: The 2010 Update", 10th International Conference of Precision Agriculture, July 18–21, 2010, Denver, Colorado, USA.
9. Popov, A. (2017). Assessment of land fragmentation of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine. Економічний часопис-XXI, 164(3-4), 56-60.
10. Salahov S. V, "Scientific works" of the scientific-research institute of Agricultural Economics, Baku, Azerbaijan, 2016
11. "Solutions for sustainable agriculture and food systems" Prepared by the Thematic Group on Sustainable Agriculture and Food Systems of the Sustainable Development Solutions Network, United Nations 2021
12. Drones in agriculture, <https://svofermerstvo.ru/svoemedia/articles/drony-v-sel-skom-hozhjaystve>
13. A report on drones belonging to the Science and Technology Park was heard at SOCAR, <https://ameaytp.az/index.php/component/content/article/88-son-x-b-r/485-socar-da-elm-v-texnologiya-park-na-m-xsus-dronlar-bar-d-m-ruz-dinl-nilib>
14. SUSTAINABLE MODERN FARMING METHODS, <https://www.webagron.com/surdurule-bilir-modern-tarim-yontemleri/>